

REPRESENTING TRANSLAMINAR FRACTURE AS A COHESIVE CRACK

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1 Introduction

In fibre-reinforced composites with UD plies, the translaminar fracture toughness [1]-[5] represents the energy dissipated per unit of projected area during the translaminar fracture of a composite ply (Fig. 1). It encompasses several energy-dissipating mechanisms, such as matrix cracking, fibre pull-out, fibre fracture and delamination, playing a key role in determining the damage tolerance of composites structures and their response during damage propagation [1]-[3][6], [7]. While this property is of significant importance for mesh-independent numerical modelling of translaminar fracture, questions still remain on for which type of laminates does the hypothesis that the translaminar damage can be represented as a crack hold. Laffan et al. [4] measured the fracture toughness of cross-ply CT specimens of different sizes and concluded that the toughness measured was specimen-independent, thus validating the concept of translaminar fracture toughness for those cross-ply specimens. The current work focuses on more realistic layups.

This paper presents experimental work on Compact Tension tests on several laminates with different combinations of 0°, 45° and 90° plies. Assuming that the damage can be represented as a single crack, the resistance curve (R-curve) for each laminate is extracted from these tests. From each R-curve, an initiation and a propagation value of toughness are obtained. Each of the toughness values is used to define a cohesive law, and the specimens are then simulated (twice) using a cohesive approach in a Finite Element Model. The results show that translaminar

damage can be accurately represented by fracture mechanics, although the accuracy decreases when several plies are blocked together (due to more diffuse damage in the specimen).

2 Experimental

Compact Tension (CT) specimens [3], with dimensions and orientation shown in Fig. 2, have been manufactured. Six specimens for each layup (Table 2) were tested according to [3], [5].

The material system used in this work is the unidirectional carbon-epoxy prepreg T800s/M21 manufactured by Hexcel. The elastic ply properties were measured using standard tests and are shown in Table 1.

Microscopy was used to identify fractographic features and it allowed to verify that the crack propagated following the direction of the initial notch, even for laminates containing 45° oriented plies or blocked plies [5]. Using X-ray, the damage zone was observed to be relatively small compared to the specimen dimensions [5].

All the specimens exhibited a clear R-Curve effect and, for each specimen, an initiation value could be defined [5]. Since the R-curves converged reaching steady-state, a propagation value for the critical energy release rate was determined [5]. For instance, for laminate E from Table 2, the corresponding R-curve is shown in Fig. 3. The effect of blocking 0° plies together increased significantly the translaminar fracture toughness value whereas blocking 45° plies affected slightly the latter due to the delamination at the ±45° interface [5].

3 Numerical simulation

The specimens from the previous section (Table 2) were modelled using FE. A whole CT specimen (Fig. 4), with a fine mesh around the crack, was modelled using 4-node bilinear plane stress (CPS4R) elements with reduced integration, and was run in Abaqus Standard [8]. The cohesive crack was modelled with 4-node cohesive elements (COH2D4) using a bi-linear law. The cohesive crack was modelled by means of a bilinear law (using in turn the initiation and propagation fracture toughness values).

Fig. 5 shows results for layout E specimens (Table 2). It can be observed that the simulations with a bi-linear cohesive law can successfully capture either the initiation or propagation part of the curve, depending on which values of toughness is used. These results, together with the results for the other laminates to be included in the full paper, show that the R-curves measured experimentally are suitable for representing the translaminar fracture process for the range of laminates selected.

4 Conclusions

By carrying out direct numerical simulations of crack propagation in CT specimens with different layups, using fracture toughness data obtained experimentally, this paper shows that:

- The models with the initiation fracture toughness correctly represent the first stage of damage, namely they capture the peak load.
- The models with the propagation fracture toughness correctly represent the latter stage of damage, namely that corresponding to the horizontal part of the R-curve.

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Fig. 1 - SEM fracture surface of a $[(90_6/-45)/(90_6/45)/90_3]_S$ specimen.

Fig. 2 - CT specimen dimensions in mm.

Table 1 – Material properties of T800s/M21.

Modulus (GPa)			Poisson's ratio
Longitudinal	Transverse	Shear	0.33
160	9.3	4.2	

Table 2 – Layups investigated [5].

ID	Layup
A	$(90)_{34}$
B	$[(90/0)_8/90]_S$
C	$[(90_6/0)_2/90_3]_S$
D	$[((90_5/0)_2)_2/90_3]_S$
E	$[(90_6/-45)/(90_6/45)/90_3]_S$
F	$[(90_5/-45/+45)/90_3]_S$
G	$[(90_6/+45/0/-45)/90_3]_S$
H	$[90/+45/0/-45]_{3S}$
I	$[90_2/0_2/+45_2/-45_2/90/0/+45/-45]_{3S}$

Fig. 3 – R-curve for $[(90_6/-45)/(90_6/45)/90_3]_S$ specimen.

Fig. 4 – CT specimen modelled in FE.

Fig. 5 - Load displacement curves for $[(90_6/-45)/(90_6/45)/90_3]_S$ specimens.